

Analysis of the Generalization of Students' Success Predictive Models in a Series of Java MOOCs on edX

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Abstract. One of the key challenges in Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) is the high attrition rate. While researchers have worked on predictive models to detect students at risk, one problem is that these models are often trained using data from one course. However, these models face difficulties when generalizing to other contexts. In this line, this work aims to analyze how predictive models can generalize to other similar courses. Particularly, analyses are conducted using a series of three courses about Java programming, with several editions in English and in Spanish, and in teacher-paced and learner-paced modes, and using variables at learner and course level. This way, it is possible to analyze the generalizability considering different combinations of predictive models to forecast MOOC grades and whether or not students pass the course. Results show that it is possible to achieve proper transferability between models in this context, although the predictive power decreases considerably in specific combinations of courses. Moreover, transferability improves when combining two courses. In addition, it is possible to achieve accurate results regardless of the language although significant differences are observed in some cases when transferring models to the courses in a different language. In contrast, there are barely differences when training and predicting using teacher-paced and learner-paced MOOCs, and accurate results are obtained in both cases. These results entail that it is possible to achieve transferable models in MOOCs when using related MOOCs although a drop in the predictive power may appear depending on the course and language.

Keywords: prediction, MOOCs, generalization, learning analytics, student's success

1 Introduction and Related Works

Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) can be very useful for lifelong learning since they offer short open courses that might be tailored to learners' needs. However, it is also very typical that learners enroll in the MOOC but they do not manage to complete it, with completion rates below 10% [1]. While there might be many possible factors

affecting this issue (e.g., psychological, social, personal, course-related, time, etc. [2]), the high attrition rates have led many researchers to analyze how to detect students at risk of failing or dropping out the course to help them. This has been mainly done through the development of predictive models using machine learning techniques.

Particularly, these models have mainly focused on dropout prediction [3] or success prediction, although other variables (e.g., students' behaviors, affective states, etc. [4] have also been explored). Regarding the variables to predict, the most typical ones have been related to interactions with exercises [5] and interactions with videos [6], with the first group often providing the most accurate results (e.g., [7]). Moreover, other works have used variables related to course activity (e.g., Alamri et al. [8], achieved powerful results using just the time spent on resources and the number of accesses), and course forum [7], among others (as suggested in [4]). As for the algorithms, many algorithms, such as regression, Random Forest, Decision Trees, neural networks, etc. have been used, although some works have reported that differences between them are smaller than the difference data could make [9].

However, one key limitation of the previous models is that they might have problems when trying to generalize to other contexts. For example, Occumpaugh et al. [10] reported difficulties when using a trained model with other students, and Boyer and Veeramachaneini [11] found a drop in the Area Under the Curve (AUC) of 0.1 when transferring the predictive models to the next edition of the MOOC. Moreover, Romero and Ventura [12] edited a special issue with several works that worked around generalizability, and some works showed that specific predictors and/or the application [13] or regularization techniques could improve generalizability [14]. Furthermore, Gitinabard et al. [15] reported that their models could be generalized to future editions of the course and even when training with a small number of students at risk. However, one limitation is that these analyses were done based on only two undergraduate courses, and more research is needed around that.

In relation to that, Sgir et al [16] highlighted the current limitations of generalizability of the models and the research results due to the use of limited contexts. A typical claim that is often reported is that results should be generalized to similar contexts, but this is not often tested. In this line, Moreno-Marcos et al. [7] analyzed predictive models using two MOOCs on the same topics and found that most of the results were generalizable, with some differences. However, more work is needed to understand the conditions that make models generalizable. Some of the previous examples (e.g., [11, 15]) focused on transferring to the next edition of the MOOC, but there are other cases that are worth analyzing to gather new insights on this topic. For example, it is interesting to analyze if the instruction language or the instruction mode (i.e., instructor-paced, when materials are released progressively; or learned paced, where all materials are available from the beginning and learners can decide when to enroll and engage with them) could affect generalization.

In this line, this work aims to contribute with new insights into this. The objective of this work is to analyze to what extent predictive models to forecast success and grades can generalize to other similar courses and/or contexts, considering the topic of Java programming. In order to do that, data from three MOOCs belonging to the same series of MOOCs about Java programming will be used. Considering this, the following

specific objectives (O) will be addressed to analyze how models can be transferred to other courses:

- O1. Analyze to what extent predictive models to forecast success and grades can generalize to other MOOCs on the same topic.
- O2. Analyze to what extent predictive models to forecast success and grades can generalize to the same MOOCs in a different language.
- O3. Analyze to what extent predictive models to forecast success and grades can generalize to the same MOOCs in a different instruction mode (teacher paced / learner paced).

The structure of this work is as follows. Section 2 presents the methodology, including details about the educational context and the sample, the variables involved in the study and the analytical methods. Section 3 details and discusses the results obtained in this work, according to the mentioned objectives, and the main conclusions, limitations and future research directions are provided and justified in Section 4.

2 Methodology

2.1 Educational context

This work is carried out using data from a series of three MOOCs about Java programming offered on edX by Universidad Carlos III de Madrid. The first course (C1) covers the basics of Java programming, use of conditionals and loops, recursion and Object-Oriented programming; the second (C2) covers aspects about error detection, unit tests, program efficiency, and software engineering; and the third one (C3) covers data structures and algorithms, including linear structures, stacks, queues, trees, and sorting algorithms. Each of the courses is organized in five modules and contains formative exercises and summative assessments in each of the modules. In these courses, it is necessary to obtain 60% of the points to pass the course, although there is no minimum grade for each assessment.

Table 1. Details of the sample size for each type of course

Course	C1 (n=15,692)		C2 (n=2,277)		C3 (n=805)	
Language	English	Spanish	English	Spanish	English	Spanish
Learner paced	5,747	948	1,259	280	354	243
Teacher paced	8,708	289	666	72	187	21

The data collection period was between 2015 and 2019, including several editions of each MOOC. Moreover, each of the three MOOCs were offered both in Spanish and English (there were six MOOCs indeed) and the courses were offered in a learner-paced mode excepting the first edition of each of the MOOCs (covered in this data collection period). The information used for these analyses is taken from the tracking logs [17]. Particularly, the following events are considered: *problem_check*, *edx.forum.comment.created*, *edx.forum.response.created*, *edx.forum.threat.created*,

edx.forum.thread.voted and *edx.forum.response.voted*. Moreover, as many students enroll in the MOOC but do not engage with it, only students who have attempted at least one summative exercise (i.e., one question in one of the exams) are considered. Details of the sample size considering these criteria are provided in Table 1.

2.2 Description of the variables and analytical methods

The dependent variables of this study are two: (1) the final grade of the MOOC, measured in scale 0-1, and (2) a binary variable representing whether or not students pass the course (i.e., obtain a grade higher or equal than 60%). Regarding the independent variables, they are classified in two groups to include variables at user levels which capture students' interactions with the MOOCs, and variables at course level that serve to indicate the main features of the course to support the generalizability of the models. Table 2 presents the full list of variables, including the dependent variables. For the predictive models related to the dependent variable are not used (e.g., *avg_sum* and *per_sum* are not used in models to predict pass).

As for the machine learning algorithms, the following algorithms are considered: Decision Trees (DT), Random Forest (RF), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) and Gradient Boosting (GB). All these algorithms have been used through the Sklearn Python library. Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) and Area Under the Curve (AUC) are used to evaluate the results when using regression and classification, respectively.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Transfer models between courses

The first analysis consists of training the model using the data until the end of the course with different combinations of courses (C) and algorithms. Particularly, models have been trained using every single course individually, combinations of two courses, and all three courses together, and these models are evaluated for each of the three courses. Results obtained for success prediction and grades predictions can be found in Tables 3 and 4, respectively. When predicting success and grades in C1, it can be observed that there are barely differences in terms of the algorithms excepting KNN, which shows poorer results. Regarding generalizability, results are stable and accurate regardless of the course to predict, except when training with C3. In this case, the sample size could affect the result as it is considerably smaller than the other courses and in fact, the predictive power when predicting in C3 is also worse than in other cases. When predicting using C2, GB offers the best results in all combinations for classification, although there are not strong differences with other algorithms and conclusions in terms of generalizability are similar. In this case, it is also interesting to see that there are combinations when C2 is predicted using a model trained with other courses and results are even slightly better. For example, model trained with C1 in DT is better than the model trained with C2. This may entail that there is a good level of transferability between MOOCs on the same topic, which is consistent with [7] when analyzing feature importance in similar courses. In addition, these results are consistent with [15], which

reported accurate results when transferring to other editions of the same course. Moreover, results generally slightly improve when combining several courses, which suggests that adding more data could boost generalizability even having different courses.

Table 2. List of variables.

Category	Variable	Description
User level	avg_sum	Average grade of summative exercises (non-attempted exercises are graded as 0)
	pass	It indicates whether or not students have obtained a grade higher or equal the passing rate (60%)
	per_ass	Percentage of attempted exams even if they are not completed (e.g., if the MOOC has 5 exams, values are multiples of 0.2)
	avg_for	Average grade of formative exercises (non-attempted exercises are graded as 0)
	per_for	Percentage of attempted formative exercises
	npart	Number of times the students have participated in the forum by creating a thread or responding a previous message in a thread
	nvotes	Number of positive votes received in forum threads and responses
	compl	It indicates whether or not students have attempted all the exams
	wload	It is a weighted average of previous factors as $0.5 \cdot \text{per_ass} + 0.4 \cdot \text{per_for} + 0.05 \cdot \text{per_votes} + 0.05 \cdot \text{per_part}$, where the last two represent nvotes and npart normalized to the maximum value in the dataset for each variable, respectively
Course level	version	Categorical value indicating the specific edition of the course (each of the three courses may have several editions in each language)
	nexercises	Number of exercises in the course (number of items in the problem folder or the course structure, including formative and summative ones)
	nvideos	Number of videos on the course
	tduration	Sum of time needed to complete the course, considering video length and 68 seconds for each question, following discussions in [2]
	language	Categorical variable to represent if the course is delivered in English or Spanish
	inst_mode	Categorical variable to represent if the course is delivered in teacher-paced or learner-paced mode
	avg_cgrade	Average grade of the course considering all students (6 possible values are present considering 3 courses in 2 languages)

The analysis of C3 is interesting because the predictive power when training with that course is not as high as in the other cases. In this case, it is observed that the predictive power when training with C1 and/or C2 is sometimes higher or equal than training with C3 (e.g., when training with C2 and DT in classification or when training with C1 or C2 and DT in regression). This suggests that models trained with very similar courses in topics and methodology could be transferable in some contexts. This result is consistent with [15], but differs from the findings in Boyer and Veeramachaneni [11], who observed a drop of 0.1 in AUC when training with data from a previous edition of the same MOOC. Nevertheless, the course context may affect the results, suggesting that transferability could be achieved (as shown in this study), but this should be evaluated in each case. Moreover, results also show that models trained with several courses could also benefit individual courses, as previously suggested in [19].

Table 3. Transference between models when predicting success (values presented in AUC).

Algorithm	DT			RF			KNN			GB		
	C1	C2	C3									
C1	0.93	0.92	0.80	0.93	0.89	0.80	0.92	0.84	0.87	0.93	0.92	0.82
C2	0.93	0.91	0.86	0.93	0.89	0.80	0.78	0.89	0.67	0.93	0.92	0.84
C3	0.86	0.86	0.81	0.86	0.87	0.80	0.80	0.74	0.73	0.88	0.89	0.84
C1+C2	0.94	0.92	0.86	0.93	0.93	0.82	0.95	0.94	0.74	0.94	0.93	0.82
C1+C3	0.94	0.92	0.86	0.93	0.91	0.84	0.94	0.72	0.83	0.93	0.92	0.88
C2+C3	0.94	0.92	0.86	0.83	0.88	0.83	0.86	0.95	0.89	0.93	0.94	0.86
All	0.92	0.91	0.84	0.94	0.93	0.84	0.94	0.92	0.82	0.93	0.94	0.86

Table 4. Transference between models when predicting grades (values presented in RMSE).

Algorithm	DT			RF			KNN			GB		
	C1	C2	C3									
C1	0.11	0.14	0.17	0.10	0.14	0.20	0.11	0.17	0.22	0.10	0.14	0.19
C2	0.11	0.13	0.18	0.11	0.13	0.18	0.15	0.15	0.30	0.11	0.13	0.17
C3	0.13	0.15	0.18	0.12	0.14	0.18	0.17	0.17	0.21	0.13	0.15	0.18
C1+C2	0.11	0.14	0.18	0.10	0.12	0.18	0.09	0.11	0.27	0.10	0.12	0.18
C1+C3	0.11	0.14	0.17	0.10	0.13	0.16	0.10	0.17	0.15	0.10	0.13	0.16
C2+C3	0.11	0.13	0.17	0.15	0.12	0.17	0.16	0.11	0.18	0.11	0.12	0.16
All	0.11	0.14	0.18	0.10	0.13	0.17	0.10	0.13	0.19	0.10	0.12	0.17

3.2 Transfer models with courses in different languages

The second analysis consists of analyzing the differences between transferability of models when using courses in different languages. In order to do that, models have been

trained using data from only the MOOCs in Spanish, only the MOOCs in English and both. In this case, as DT, RF and GB offered similar results, models have only been computed using GB. Results from these analyses are presented in Table 5. From this table, it can be observed that models trained with courses in English offer better results. In this case, a drop of 0.04 in AUC is observed when training with courses in Spanish and 0.01 in RMSE. These differences might be attributed to the differences between the students and/or the sample and although they are higher than those presented in the previous Section, they do not considerably impact the impact as the AUC/RMSE are still excellent to be used. When training with MOOCs in Spanish, a drop of 0.1 in AUC and 0.01 in RMSE is also observed, which is not very significant and might be due to the differences in context. Moreover, when training with both courses, no improvement is observed in classification methods with respect to training with the same language, but a slight improvement is shown in regression. Overall, results from this section might suggest that course language might have a slight effect depending on the languages and while this might affect accuracy, models might still be accurate enough to be useful for prediction. Nevertheless, if the predictive power is fair in other contexts, the impact of these differences might become more significant.

Table 5. Transference between predictive models with courses in different languages

Predictive task	Success (AUC)		Grades (RMSE)	
	Spanish	English	Spanish	English
Spanish	0.84	0.90	0.14	0.12
English	0.83	0.94	0.15	0.11
Both	0.84	0.94	0.13	0.10

Table 6. Transference between predictive models with courses in instruction modes

Predictive task	Success (AUC)		Grades (RMSE)	
	Teacher paced	Learner paced	Teacher paced	Learner paced
Teacher paced	0.93	0.93	0.10	0.13
Learner paced	0.91	0.92	0.11	0.13
Both	0.93	0.93	0.10	0.12

3.3 Transfer models with courses with different instruction modes

The third analysis consists of analyzing the differences between training using data from teacher-paced and learner-paced editions from the same courses. For this case, GB is used for classification and regression and results are presented in Table 6. From this table, little differences are observed between the models. When training with teacher-paced courses, it is noteworthy that results slightly improve for learner-paced MOOCs respect to the predictive power when training with learner-paced MOOCs but the difference is only 0.01. Moreover, the predictive power drops 0.02 in AUC when predicting success (and 0.01 in RMSE in grades prediction) in teacher-paced MOOCs

and training with learner-paced MOOCs. Nevertheless, differences are very small in all cases, which might suggest that the instruction mode does not affect transferability of the models to other courses.

4 Conclusions

This paper analyzes to what extent models trained with one course can be transferred to other courses in the same series of three MOOCs on Java programming, and the impact of the course language and instruction mode in the generalizability of the models. Results have shown that it is possible to achieve accurate results in both success prediction and grades prediction when training using data from other courses in the series although a drop of accuracy is observed in some cases (particularly when training with C3, probably due to the course context and/or reduced sample size). Moreover, results improved when combining several courses, which might suggest that the variability of courses when training might be beneficial. In the analysis of languages, results showed that there was a drop when training using data from the course in a different language, and the drop was higher in English than in Spanish. However, despite losing predictive power, the loss was less than 0.05 in AUC and 0.01 at most in RMSE, so the validity of these models to support possible interventions is not significantly affected. In addition, analyses of the instruction mode indicated low differences between teacher-paced and learner-paced modes, which might entail that models using different instruction models could be transferred without losing significant accuracy.

The implications of this work are that given the accurate levels of transferability across different editions of the course, languages and methodologies, MOOC providers could collect data from the courses they have and develop the predictive models so they could be used in other editions of the course. For example, when a new series of MOOCs is designed, predictive models could be developed using the first course and used in other courses while data are collected. Moreover, data from different editions and courses in a series of MOOCs could be combined to further improve the models. With these models, it could also be possible to design automatically targeted interventions to mitigate dropout (as was shown in a pilot in [20]).

Despite having obtained these findings, there are some limitations that are worth mentioning. First, these analyses have been carried out using just one series of three MOOCs. While they serve to gather insights about generalizability when having similar courses, which is relevant, these results are framed in a specific scenario. Thus, other conclusions might be obtained when generalizing to more heterogeneous educational contexts. Moreover, the sample size might have slightly affected the results since there was an unbalanced distribution between the different courses and languages. Furthermore, only students who engaged in exercises were considered and while this could be a reasonable approach, this could introduce certain bias.

Considering the previous limitations, future work should focus on expanding this research to more different MOOCs to gather more insights about the generalizability in different contexts. Moreover, it would be interesting to analyze the effect of the specific variables to know to what extent the course-related variables have an impact on the

transferability of the models and the possible differences in the predictive power over time. In addition, other new variables, which are not considered in this work, could be included in the model and that could have an important role for generalization. Finally, it would be relevant to put these models into practice and transfer models from previous courses, as suggested in this paper, to evaluate the real impact these models might have to reduce academic failure in the MOOC.

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